

Evaluation of Community Influence on Spouse Selection

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Abstract

In accordance with the research on the effect of resources on the choice of spouses, it is seen that the amount of material resources came to the forefront of "luxury" and "needs" among the individual's spouse selection tips. Although the amount of time sources also affects the diversity

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of clues, for a long time researchers, draw attention to the effect of clues resources only. Although we should not ignore the role of time sources, this is usually ignored. For this reason, in this article and other criteria for the selection of spouses, we wanted to provide a research quality with literature screening by drinking the elements that will attract more attention, regardless of the ranking of importance. Related research on the effect of time on decision -making proposes to learn courses and examine the spouse selection from the decision -making perspective. In addition, the existing research on the effect of resources on the choice of spouses gives the information and data about the effect of the society with different perspectives but focuses more on the results and neglects to examine the process. Therefore, based on relevant theories, this article makes several theoretical assumptions regarding the mechanism of action regarding the mechanism of action of the source existence on the actor-Partner effect on this article, spouse selection decisions, gender differences and actor-partner effect. The choice of spouse is an important connection in the continuous development of human society and a complex decision -making problem (Svenson, 1996; Candolin , 2003; li et al., 2016d). The choice of spouses includes not only tips preferences in the selection of individuals, but also the methods used by individuals in the selection of spouses (Liu et al., 2011). As an important bargaining trump card in the selection of spouses, resources have attracted the attention of many researchers by playing a decisive role in the decision -making process, including the influence of the society (Buss , 1989; Yong and Li, 2012; Li et al., 2016a; Chen and Yao, 2018; Tian et al., 2019).

Key words: *Spouse Selection, Society Effect in Spouse Selection, Society Effect in Marriage, Spouse Selection Reasons and Results*

1. Login

Culture and society determine some criteria, especially in choosing a spouse. It is evident that culture also influences individual preferences for mate cues by many other factors, such as actual sex ratio, values, mate value, aesthetic standards, mate selection intent, and ability to acquire resources (Buss , 1989; Chang et al., 2011; Durante). et al., 2012; Dillon et al., 2013). It should be noted that most research on mate choice in modern societies is based on data that

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may or may not reflect actual sexual behavior (eg, stated preferences, personal advertisements). This includes, in summary;

- (a) men with higher social status (but not women) were found to have more sexual partners, suggesting that male status is an important criterion for selecting women;*
- (b) the number of females (not males) partners decreases linearly with age, suggesting that female reproductive potential is an important criterion for male selection; and*
- (c) women (but not men) show a significant relationship between dissolution and mixed sexuality, suggesting that female sexual privilege is an important criterion in male selection.*

These results are discussed in relation to understanding mate selection mechanisms from behavioral data. Individuals often learn from others, and selection for social learning mechanisms may occur when there are costs involved in acquiring accurate behavioral information through individual learning. In terms of mate choices and preferences, it may be beneficial to use the judgment of others if it allows an individual to evaluate potential mates more quickly and efficiently than through individual trial and error. Indeed, there are potentially enormous costs if individuals choose their mates badly, if escape, infidelity or violence poses very real risks (mate choice in modern societies, Daniel Pérusse).

Status of partnership or joint decision making and using multiple elements together, simple presence and attitude towards men, as well as physical characteristics of the observed pattern may also play a role in the social transmission of preference. Previous research has shown that men and women are influenced by the obvious choices of same-sex attractive members in their attractiveness judgments. Sigall and Landy used real individuals to show that positive traits are more often attributed to men paired with attractive rather than unattractive women. Such a phenomenon suggests a more complex form of mate selection duplication. In this way, women can evaluate the attractiveness of a partner that a man can obtain in order to judge the man's own attractiveness. Another study using images presented with an imaginary partner showed that both men and women find a face paired with an attractive partner more attractive for a long-term but not short-term relationship than a face paired with an unattractive partner. Other

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studies have shown a similar effect for women who rate the attractiveness of men. Long-term preference-specific effects in humans suggest that social information is used to extract non-physical traits that make a good long-term partner, such as resources or intelligence that may be difficult to detect from physical appearance alone (Little AC, Burriss RP, Jones BC, Debruine LM, Caldwell CA 2008. *Evol . Hum. Beh .* 29).

2. Long Term Relationship of Couples

To date, studies on humans have focused on the effects of social learning on the perceptions of specific target individuals. In other words, these studies have only explored how certain patterns increase the attractiveness of paired individual targets. However, there are obvious disadvantages to being attracted to individuals who are already together, especially people with whom couples can stay in long-term relationships. Although people pursue short-term strategies, the effects of social learning on preferences in humans seem to focus more on long-term preferences than short-term preferences. However, the potential to avoid mates will allow social learners to take advantage of other people's choices. The generalization made as individuals learn the characteristics of the chosen ones and find these characteristics attractive in other individuals also provides a solution to this problem. Generalization is probably also an important component in spreading preferences for certain traits in a population. Therefore, generalization will be important in creating cross-cultural variation in preferences (Wade MJ, Pruett-Jones SG 1990, USA 87).

Agreement within a culture and differences between cultures can make attractiveness the result of learning, at least in part, by examining the choices of others in the population. Copying traits of others' choices rather than favoring a particular individual can lead to spreading agreement about which individuals and traits are attractive in a culture. Since arbitrary choices may arise in different cultures, social learning results in cultures that value different characteristics and individuals with these characteristics . Of course, arbitrary selection itself is not adaptive, but may be the result of adaptive mechanisms operating on neutral properties. Using the judgment of others can allow copying of fit-important features as well as other arbitrary features. Social learning can also influence evolutionarily relevant traits in adaptive ways, acting to adjust

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individuals to locally adaptive traits. For example, there is a great deal of variation in male preferences, and it has been suggested that this is linked to evolutionarily related tradeoffs in the choice of mates. If masculinity is more or less valuable under certain circumstances, then social learning may provide a mechanism that encourages following locally adaptive choices. In this way, social learning mechanisms:

- (i) *can reinforce relatively culturally invariant preferences for traits that predict universally adaptive outcomes,*
- (ii) *may lead to culturally variable preferences for traits whose adaptive value depends on ecological conditions, and*
- (iii) *can encourage.*

The spread of preferences for traits that do not serve an adaptive function when they arise in a population reveals that there are also possible biases towards preferences for certain traits, such as symmetry, and that these preferences may appear independent of learning, but that learning can affect them (Little A., Perrett D. 2002, 15, 28-32).

Previous studies on mate choice have focused on copying-like effects on the preferences of certain individuals. In other words, a particular individual has been shown to become more attractive when paired with an attractive partner. This is also evident in the non-human animal literature; Here, acceptance or rejection of potential mates is simply defined based on their acceptance or rejection by others. However, the duplication effects may be more general; females show preferences for new males that are physically similar to males observed in other females. This generalization of preferences for particular traits, not just for particular individuals, is important as it allows social transmission to have broader implications on the evolution of particular anatomical traits and preferences (Laland KN 1994, Theor . Popul . Biol . 45, 1-15).

3. Mate Selection and Classical Theories

Classical theories surrounding mate selection stipulate that an individual's genotype and phenotype will select a particular mate based on traits that are attractive to that individual, and that these traits and preferences are selected for them over generations (Darwin, 1859, 1871;

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Fisher, 1930; Zahavi, 1975; Kodric-Brown & Brown, 1984). Regardless of the mechanism(s) involved in choosing a mate, these theories imply that the selector makes a choice independently, that is, without further information provided by congeners or possibly heterospecifics. The net result is that individuals are more likely to choose what they perceive to be high-quality spouses than low-quality spouses, and by doing so they derive indirect and direct fitness benefits (Andersson, 1994). Thus, the key requirement of these classical theories of mate selection is that an individual's ability to identify and discriminate between suitors depends on that individual's ability to recognize and subsequently select high-quality opposite-sex congeners (Andersson & Simmons, 2006).

sound production and chemical cues indicating phenotype and genotype can be used to distinguish potential mates. Female water droplets (*Anthus spinoletta*) (Rehsteiner et al., 1998), European starlings (*Sturnus vulgaris*) (Eens et al., 1991), wolf spiders (*Hygrolycosa rubrofasciata*) (Kotiaho et al., 1996) and crickets (*Gryllus lineaticeps*) (Wagner & Reiser, 2000), all found that males choose mates based on certain aspects of their songs/calls, such as duration and complexity. Additionally, meadow voles (*Microtus pennsylvanicus*), higher free gonadal than those with lower titers steroid Adults with titers preferred the olfactory cues of their opposite-sex counterparts (Ferkin et al., 2017). higher gonadal sex steroid Male and female prairie voles with high titers of prairie voles are more likely to be successful fathers than those with lower titers of such hormones (Ferkin et al., 2017). House mice (*Mus musculus*) prefer mates with a genetically different parent tissue compatibility complex than those with a similar major tissue compatibility complex (Eklund, 1997). Presumably, this mating preference functions to provide 'good genes' for the individual's offspring, as the major tissue compatibility complex regulates immunological self/non-self-recognition (Penn & Potts, 1999) and tissue compatibility complex heterozygosity enhances reproductive success (Thoss et al., 2011). Collectively, these studies have shown that preferences for opposite-sex-specific species favor those with better genes and phenotypes, and that preference for such higher-quality individuals is typically independent of mate choices displayed by congeners.

(a) Signals and clues used for mate selection

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Signals and cues used for mate selection are usually directed towards a specific target(s), but can also be detected by non-target individuals (Dugatkin , 1992; Danchin et al., 2004; Valone , 2007). These signals and clues can provide clear information to rival peers. The unintended (non-target) receiver can then respond to these signals and cues and change their behavior towards the sender or intended receiver based on the information obtained (Danchin et al., 2004; Witte et al., 2015; Ferkin & Ferkin). , 2017). Therefore, behavioral interactions between opposite-sex peers are also a source of social information for individuals (Danchin et al., 2004; Valone , 2007). This social information, which an individual obtains by observing his peers, can be used to influence an individual's mate choice, if the individual does not have personal information about such peers (Ferkin , 2018, 2019a, b). Therefore, the net effect is that individuals can use personal information, social information, or both to facilitate mate selection, and that personal information alone provides more accurate and reliable information than social information.

(b) The effect of social information on mate choice

A growing body of evidence suggests that social information can also affect mate choice, resulting in non-independent mate choice (Dugatkin , 1992; Pruett-Jones , 1992; Witte et al., 2015). Some of the first empirical evidence of non-independent mate selection, particularly mate selection duplication, began to surface in the early 1990s with the work of Dugatkin & Godin (1992) on guppies from Trinidad. In their research, female guppies were placed in the middle of a field with two aquariums containing males of similar length at opposite ends adjacent to the central aquarium. The female guppy was able to swim freely in the aquarium she was placed in. The time spent with each man was compared, and the preferred man was the one he spent the most time with. Once a preference was determined, a model female was placed behind a Plexiglas spacer next to the originally unfavored male; the preferred male did not receive any models. The focal female was then observed as observing both the initially favored and non-preferred male. Dugatkin & Godin (1992) found that female guppies shift their preference towards the male which was not initially preferred by spending more time next to her. Thus, the association of the non-preferred male with a model female was sufficient to divert the focal female's preference from the initially preferred male and the other female 's "selection"

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of the other female, in this case the previously non-preferred male. More importantly, female guppies used social information gathered by observing a relationship between congeners to change their preference for a male. The change in the focus female's preference is due to the social information she has acquired by observing the behavioral interaction of the model female and the male she did not initially prefer. Thus, the result is true that females do not make an independent mate selection. Instead, they use social information to make a non-independent mate choice (Dugatkin , 1992; Pruett-Jones , 1992; Witte et al., 2015).

(c) Type and frequency of social information

Among the effects of society, research has been carried out on the relations of social knowledge with other living things. The mating system can affect the type and frequency of social information, which can affect individuals' mate selection decisions. Vakirtzis (2011) compiled the results of studies for various species and classified them according to whether mate selection duplication was found, not found, or inconclusive. Vakirtzis (2011) also gave information about the mating system of the species. The majority of mate selection duplication studies have been conducted on species with a random mating system; Fewer studies have been done on species thought to be polygamous and monogamous. Vakirtzis (2011) determined that among the random species studied, most showed mate selection duplication. Similarly, Vakirtzis (2011) found conflicting reports of mate selection duplication in two monogamous types. Perhaps males and females within the same species may differ in whether they participate in non-independent mate selection and whether the factors influencing such a decision are the same. It is also possible that the mode of external or internal fertilization influences the propensity for mate selection to occur for duplication or non-independent mate selection. However, data are limited to support any of these potential hypotheses.

4. The Role of Parental Care

Another consideration regarding the effects of the mating system on non-independent mate selection decisions is the degree to which males and females provide parental care. In general, females are generally considered to be the more selective sex due to their higher initial

reproductive investment (Trivers , 1972), which may explain why non-independent mate selection is tested more often in females than in female birds and fish. Therefore, Frommen et al. (2009) suggested that mate selection should be more common in species that show parental care and in sexes that provide more parental care. Possibly, mate selection will occur more frequently in the sexes with greater reproductive expenditure.

A model individual provides three types of information to the focal individual:

- (a) *phenotype and genotype of the model ,*
- (b) *behavior of a model towards a fellow of the opposite sex, and*
- (c) *the behavior of a fellow of the opposite sex towards the model.*

can influence the use of social information for an individual's mate choice(s). However, the focus is on whether the individual will respond in a particular way, determine whether the clues provide information and whether the information provided is reliable (Wheeler et al. 2011; Ferkin , 2018, 2019a, b).

phenotype and genotype of a potential competitor or model provide social information that can influence individuals' mate choice (Kodric -Brown, 1985; Penn & Potts , 1999; Thoss et al., 2011). The mating system can affect the type and frequency of social information, which can affect individuals' mate selection decisions. Vakirtzis (2011) compiled the results of studies for various species and classified them according to whether mate selection duplication was found, not found, or inconclusive. Vakirtzis (2011) also gave information about the mating system of the species. Vakirtzis (2011) determined that among the random species studied, most showed mate selection duplication. At present, there is no consensus among studies as to whether the systems involved are a good indicator of whether a species is engaged in non-independent mate selection. This concern is highlighted by the fact that many studies have examined the possibility of non-independent mate selection occurring in only one sex (Forsgren et al., 1996). Perhaps males and females within the same species may differ in whether they participate in non-independent mate selection and whether the factors influencing such a decision are the same. It is also possible that the mode of external or internal fertilization influences the propensity for mate selection to occur for duplication or non-independent mate selection. However, data are limited to support any of these potential hypotheses. Another consideration

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5. The Role of Social Interactions

There are two hypotheses about the role of social interactions. First, the hypothesis that social environment influences mate preferences was tested. This hypothesis predicts that focal females' mate preferences will differ in various compositions of the social environment. Second, the hypothesis of genetic variation in the influence of social environment on mate preferences was tested. This hypothesis predicts that the mate preferences of the focal females will be different due to the full sibling family. In other words, there must be a family influence. This result suggests that the genetic makeup of sibling families contributes to differences in mate preferences of focal females (Kodric -Brown, 1985; Penn & Potts , 1999; Thoss et al., 2011).

Arranged marriages have also been compared with free-choice marriages from cultures with natural fertility. The study was conducted on three different traditional Homo sapiens populations with natural contraception . The aim is to establish the relationship between the type of marriage and the number of children. To the authors' knowledge, this is the first study to examine the reproductive benefits of free-selection mating in humans. The societies studied

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are culturally diverse and live in different parts of the world. The results of this research, showing the same characteristics in general, have worsened the effect of the society on mate selection, and the continuation of their partnerships in bad directions (Arranged mate selection does not affect reproductive success in humans; Piotr Sorokowski , Agata Groyecka , Maciej Karwowski , Upma Manral , Amit Kumar, Agnieszka NiemczykMichalina _ _ Marczak , Michał Misiak , Agnieszka Marczak , Thomas Huanca & Bogusaw , Bogdan Wojcisz and Bogusaw , Bogdan WoJciske and Boguska , Bogdan WoJciske , Esther Conde).

6. Social Perspective on Community Impact

It should be noted that society is on a mission to realize many of its fundamental interests, such as protecting and maintaining itself. Accordingly, the concept of a community of collaborating people, having a relative continuity, generally sharing a certain geographical location, common culture and history, is correct. With these features, the society gains a separate feature and definition when it is separated from the random or temporary crowds of people (Ozankaya , 1986: 3).

Particularly, according to the national and international studies conducted in recent years, it is seen that research and scientific studies on the subject of mate selection have increased. Preferences and priorities in choosing a spouse according to gender have been different in recent years (Buss and Barnes , 1986). It would be appropriate to compare men 's interest in the fertility rate for the continuation of their lineage with other preferences . This reveals that physical characteristics and health status are very important in choosing a spouse (Buss et al., 2001; Schopenhauer , 2018). It is seen that the criteria for the selection of women are different. It is seen that these include men's more attractive romantic and socio -economic status and social status issues (Yıldırım, 2007: 17; Güllü, 2018: 44). With the choice of a spouse, a family and togetherness are established. Since it is a process that takes place within the framework of the individual's consent and is based on a formal contract, this means that the family undertakes some social roles and duties together with marriage (Güllü, 2018: 43). The family is the smallest building block of society. This union and contract are evaluated within the framework of many different approaches and theories. Many theories can be derived from here:

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- (a) *structural-functional family theory (Persosns , 1975),*
- (b) *symbolic interaction (Herbert Mead , 1934 and Herbert Blumer , 1969),*
- (c) *social conflict (Marx , 1850),*
- (d) *family systems,*
- (e) *feminist, developmental approach,*
- (f) *bio- social and family ecology theories,*

are some of these theories (Hammond , 2010: 55; Yener, 2018:870).

In recent years, there have been many studies on the family. It is obvious that these studies make significant contributions to science and literature (Jary and Jary , 1991; İçli, 1997; Öz, 2008; Gökler, 2008; Gökçearsan Çiftçi, 2014; Gökçe, 2017; Yener, 2018).

health of social change , material and spiritual cultural elements must change together, that is, in parallel with each other. Material culture changes (inventions, inventions) have been faster than spiritual cultural changes (tradition, custom, philosophy, law, etc.), especially in industrial societies (Doğan, 1998: 287). In other words, it is possible to say that the material and moral gains and negative effects of the social change process are related to the inevitable effects of human beings remaining at the primitive society level (Guvenc, 1999: 103).

7. The Essential Dynamics of the Social Process

It has been determined that the industrial revolution of women led to the process of social change and caused significant developments in the situation of women in the social structure (Dallos , 1990: 385). In other words, we can conclude from this that women are no longer in the background, considering that their perception of life is affected besides their social status. It is important that the concept of being under control by men is now replaced by the behavior of questioning the one-sided relationship style (Ergil, 1994: 222). Although the situation was different until the middle of the twentieth century, relations in the extended family showed strongly vertical characteristics. In this case, the fact that the authority line is clearly from top to bottom should not be attributed to coincidence. In the meantime, it is necessary to remember that one of the rules in the family structure is about who will marry whom. This decision was taken by the elders of the family in a definite and undisputed way (Rothrauff , 2005: 63).

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Despite this, the situation has changed in modern society life after the industrial revolution. Contrary to the situation in the feudal social structure, people no longer marry their neighbor's daughter or son, or even girls and boys with whom they often share their religion and common cultural traits.

Again, when the rapid social change processes after industrialization are evaluated, it can be thought that a marriage institution in a local structure continues to exist depending on geographical, cultural, social and economic factors (Yazan, 1991: 473).

It should be remembered that in Turkey, with some exceptions, the institution of marriage is carried out together with the imam marriage, with the official marriage being the basis. Marrying only according to imam marriage is prohibited by the Civil Code (Akyüz, 1991: 308). According to a study carried out by Hacettepe University Institute of Population Studies (2003), 10836 households were reached in the sample group, which was stated to be representative of the Turkish population, and a total of 8075 women in the 15-49 age group who lived in these households and had at least one previous marriage were interviewed. According to the research results; In Turkey, there has been a great decrease in marriages made only according to imam marriage. In 1968, the rate of those who got married only with an imam marriage was 15%. In 2003, this rate decreased to 5.8%. In our country, the family institution is faced with a wide variety of risks. One of the most important problems faced by the family institution is the rapid increase in divorce rates. Arıkan (1996: 21) in his study named "Research on public attitudes towards divorce" stated that when compared to other countries universally, the divorce rate in our country is less than 1 per thousand, therefore, divorce cannot be considered as a social problem in the social dimension.

Considering the provinces for Turkey, the highest divorce rate is seen in İzmir with 2.39 per thousand. It should be noted that this rate is in parallel with those in Western European countries. The lowest divorce rate is 0.11 per thousand in Hakkari and Siirt provinces (TÜİK 2008). It is observed that divorce rates, which are seen as a social problem of modern society, are low in Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia regions. However, this is due to the fact that divorce is seen as "taboo" under the influence of traditional rules. According to Doğan (1998: 238), divorce rates are higher in marriages made through "love" or "flirting" than in traditional marriages known as arranged marriages.

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8. Conclusion and Recommendations

After the industrial revolution, strict rules specific to feudal culture could not resist change. This necessitated the evaluation of new data in modern society. The effect of the change experienced for modern society has caused a decrease in marriage rates in terms of industrialized countries, which are called welfare societies. With the increase in divorce rates, alternative lifestyles including living alone or common-law partnerships are emerging. High income per capita falls in welfare societies. The robustness of social security systems reveals less risk of facing financial problems for divorced people and their children. When evaluated in terms of minimum living standards, women and children may face financial problems as well as moral problems in cases of family break-up for developing countries that are behind industrialized societies. Suggestions in this regard can be listed as follows:

- (a) For new generations, it should be prevented from seeing marriage as just a contract. The widespread cultural awareness that healthy marriages are raising happy children by establishing a regular family life needs to be better processed and taught.*
- (b) to marry in order to have children, it is necessary to prevent presenting the magazine elements that make marriage and divorce ordinary as a role model to society and youth through mass media.*
- (c) Marriage counseling should be provided by the state, both before and after marriage, compulsory and free of charge.*
- (d) It is very important to consider the marriage counseling mechanism, which will provide marriage counseling services, in the master's and doctoral programs of universities.*
- (e) Adults should demonstrate exemplary behavior in their children's marital and harmonious spousal relationship.*
- (f) Supportive and educational services should be provided to children with divorce.*
- (g) Measures should be taken so that social problems such as poverty and unemployment do not affect the relations of the spouse and family.*

9. resources

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